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Mapping Metadata - Improving Dataset Discipline Classification¹

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Introduction

There is increasing interest in developing metrics for datasets (Cousijn et al., 2019) but investigations into data sharing, reuse and citation practices remain relatively nascent. The lack in research and indicator development is, in part, due to the limited amount of metadata for published datasets, in particular discipline information.

In this paper, we present some efforts from the Meaningful Data Counts (MDC) project to improve discipline classification for datasets available in DataCite. Specifically, we describe two case studies on mapping existing discipline classification systems to the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development's (OECD) revised Field of Science and Technology

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(FOS) discipline classification system (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, 2007) and the lessons we have learned.

Background

The MDC team relies on DataCite as a source for bibliometric analyses of dataset metadata in an attempt to characterize data sharing, reuse and citation with the ultimate goal to develop benchmarks and metrics that help to demonstrate the value of research data as first-class scholarly outputs (Morissette et al., 2020). DataCite is an international, non-profit organization that has assigned DOIs for research data and other artifacts since 2009. DataCite aggregates metadata and citations for datasets and has been the source of some past bibliometric investigations of datasets (Dudek et al., 2019; Mongeon et al., 2017). Robinson-Garcia et al. (2017) specifically explored the characteristics of DataCite to determine the possibility of using it as a new bibliometric data source to analyze datasets as a scholarly output.

There are six mandatory metadata fields required for all datasets in DataCite according to the DataCite Metadata Schema (DataCite Metadata Working Group, 2021), listed in Table 1. Additionally, 14 metadata fields can be optionally included such as (most importantly to this project) their discipline classification. For those datasets that include subject information, DataCite has specified that the OECD FOS discipline classification system be adopted in 2020.

Table 1. Mandatory Fields in the DataCite Metadata Schema.

<i>Field</i>	<i>Description</i>
Identifier	The Identifier is a unique string that identifies a resource.
Creator	The main researchers involved in producing the data, or the authors of the publication, in priority order.
Title	A name or title by which a resource is known.
Publisher	The name of the entity that holds, archives, publishes prints, distributes, releases, issues, or produces the resource.
Publication Year	The year when the data was or will be made publicly available.
Resource Type	A description of the resource.

Since discipline is an optional metadata field, it is important to record how much coverage there is for dataset discipline classifications. On April 19th, 2022, there were 11,755,036 total datasets on DataCite. Of those datasets, 666,197 (5.67%) have a discipline listed, 113,615 (0.97%) have been formally cited, and only 2,181 (0.02%) have a discipline and a citation. These findings reflect similar findings about dataset metadata on DataCite (Ninkov et al., 2021) and can be automatically reproduced via a Jupyter notebook (Ninkov, 2021). The implications of the lack of metadata on disciplines in DataCite has prevented the analysis discipline specific data sharing and reuse. Other metadata fields that are often used to derive subject information, such as title or abstracts provide only sparse information or are entirely absent (Robinson-Garcia et al., 2017).

In order to investigate how and why people use and cite datasets and to develop meaningful metrics for research data, better and more complete discipline classifications of datasets are needed. Ideally, metadata providers (i.e. data repositories, researchers, publishers) could help to improve the current situation by working to create complete metadata records that include discipline classification to put their data into context. This would not only support bibliometric

analyses and indicator development but would also improve data discovery (Gregory et al., 2020). However, even when discipline information is available there is an additional required step of mapping the often diverse classification systems together for larger scale studies. This task of mapping different systems together comes with challenges such as determining which of the many various discipline classification systems to use, understanding the definitions of what is meant by a discipline classification and deciding how to deal with outputs that are interdisciplinary in nature (Lee et al., 2012; Wang & Waltman, 2016). These represent typical problems in library science when it comes to cross-linking controlled vocabularies (e.g., via cross-concordances; Mayr & Petras, 2008).

Mapping discipline classifications to enhance metadata for datasets

In an effort to improve dataset discipline classifications in DataCite, the two following mapping case studies were conducted. By describing and reflecting on these two different, yet related, case studies, the overall challenges and opportunities that come with mapping different discipline classification systems for datasets can be better understood. The lessons learned at the intersection of these two case studies can additionally assist in the development of new approaches to discipline classification for datasets (e.g. automatic approaches using machine learning).

Case Study 1 - Mapping the DFG Fachsystematik to OECD FOS

The MDC team in collaboration with DataCite and re3data (<https://www.re3data.org/>) developed a rules-based approach to discipline classifications (Garza et al., 2021) with data collected from the 2014 version of the German Research Foundation's (DFG) discipline classification system (Fachsystematik) (Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft, 2014) to the FOS classification system (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, 2007). The FOS classification system is part of the Frascati Manual, which recommends that the major fields of science and technology should be adopted as the functional fields of a scientific classification system. The FOS classification includes six top-level categories (e.g., *Natural sciences*) and 42 subcategories (e.g., *Physical sciences*).

The Fachsystematik is the discipline classification system used by the DFG to organize funding programs and grant applications. It consists of four hierarchies including four scientific areas at the highest hierarchical level (e.g., 3 - *Natural Sciences*), 14 subject areas (e.g. 32 - *Physics*), 48 review boards (e.g., 307 - *Condensed Matter Physics*), and 213 disciplines at the lowest hierarchical level (e.g., 307-02 - *Theoretical Condensed Matter Physics*). The Fachsystematik was a particularly interesting system to map to OECD FOS because it is used by re3data (re3data.org) to classify data repositories. Most repositories in re3data are assigned at least one notation at the third level (i.e., the review boards) of the Fachsystematik. If these notations were mapped to FOS notations, re3data metadata describing repositories could supplement metadata records in DataCite, resulting in an increase of the coverage of subject information in DataCite from the current 5.67% to anywhere between 20% and 40%.

The mapping process consisted of five steps:

1. Creating a candidate correspondence mapping using the specifications of the Fachsystematik and FOS classification systems. We generated this by identifying similar notations in the documentations mentioned above. As a general rule, only the higher levels of granularity in both vocabularies were mapped.

2. Reviewing the candidate correspondence (via three 1 hour virtual meetings and independent review of the mapping between meetings)
3. Documenting alignment issues (see discussion)
4. Opening the final version of the candidate correspondence to public comments on the PID Forum website (pidforum.org) and multiple social networks from 2021-09-01 to 2021-10-01.
5. Addressing comments by the community

Steps 4 and 5 are important to the process because, for example, discipline classifications can be subjective and depending on the use case of the discipline classification system can be different. However, we must note that we did not receive and therefore did not address comments by the community. However, we think that it is still an important step to report to both showcase our efforts to include community feedback in the process as well as to repeat the call to the community in any future mapping efforts.

The final mapping includes at least one notation from OECD FOS for each notation of the Fachsystematik. *Biological Sciences* (43) and *Clinical Medicine* (27) are the FOS notations with the most Fachsystematik notations mapped to them. Meanwhile, eight FOS notations were assigned with a single Fachsystematik notation. Figure 1 shows the distribution of Fachsystematik notations mapped to FOS notations. The full mapping file can be found in Zenodo (Garza et al., 2022).

Figure 1. Distribution of DFG Fachsystematik notations mapped to first and second level FOS notations (Garza et al., 2022).

Case Study 2 - Mapping NSF discipline classification system to OECD FOS

Datasets are often associated with publications that are indexed in bibliographic databases and that contain discipline information and other additional metadata. Using the link between datasets and journal articles, datasets can be classified by proxy (Mongeon et al., 2017). For example, the Observatoire des Sciences et des Technologies (OST) uses the National Science Foundation's (NSF) discipline classification system to classify journals in their local Web of Science database. The NSF discipline classification has three hierarchies: two larger disciplines

at the highest level (e.g., *Natural Sciences and Engineering*), 14 disciplines (e.g., *Physics*) and 144 sub-disciplines (e.g., *Applied Physics*). The journal-publication-dataset-relation will be exploited to complete disciplinary information for datasets. As of April 19, 2022, there are 6,106,165 datasets on DataCite that have publications connected to them. In this case study the discipline classification from the NSF was manually mapped to the classification system of the FOS.

The NSF-to-FOS mapping exercise was first carried out by searching for components of the NSF subfield names in the FOS documentation using a case-insensitive string matching. Then, based on the number of exact matches, NSF subdisciplines were assigned to one of the 42 FOS disciplines. Of the 144 NSF subdisciplines, 10 had to be mapped to multiple FOS disciplines. For these 10 NSF subdisciplines, the mapping was carried out on the journal level in order to match individual journals to exactly one FOS category. Most journals were reclassified based on their titles. If titles were not informative enough, journal scope statements (from journal websites) were taken into account. In summary, the complete mapping procedure of NSF subdisciplines and journals included preprocessing of journal names and classes, use of alternative journal and class descriptions, mapping strategies in case of conflicts, manual review and is summarized in a flow chart displayed in Figure 2 (Jambor, 2022). The procedure highlights the complexity of mapping exercises (e.g., Lee et al., 2012) but it also demonstrates where automatic interventions may aid future implementations.

Figure 2. Flow chart of NSF-to-OECD mapping process (Jambor, 2022).

Discussion

Mapping classification systems to one another is a messy, yet necessary, undertaking to address the problem of the lack of discipline classification contained within the metadata of datasets. In both case studies presented in this paper, the challenges of performing mapping exercises were presented. This section discusses these challenges, lessons learned, and future directions.

In the case studies presented, alignment issues were observed between the two classification systems for a variety of reasons. The issues stem from the fact that (1) the interdisciplinary subjects are modeled differently in the different classifications, (2) the classifications are structured differently, and (3) the classifications were developed for different reasons (e.g., OECD was developed for measuring R&D, Fachsystematik for managing grants, and NSF was developed for classifying journals). Some highlights of these issues in practice include:

- Hierarchies are modeled differently in different classifications. For example, *Social Sciences* in the Fachsystematik was the only case where a notation of the least granularity in the FOS was used in the mapping. Another example is the NSF subdisciplines of the field *Clinical Medicine* mapping to FOS disciplines outside of *Clinical Medicine* based on different interpretations of the discipline.

- Astronomy is a notation in the Fachsystematik that maps to the notation *Physical Sciences* in FOS. As a result, granularity is lost and a highly specific research area is ascribed to a general category.
- FOS differentiates between humans and animals in biomedical and biotechnological categories whereas the Fachsystematik does not. For example, in FOS notations, the discipline *Animal Biotechnology* is supposed to be included in the discipline *Agricultural Biotechnology*. In Fachsystematik notations, however, this is encompassed in the *Biomedical Technology and Medical Physics* notation.
- Some of the disciplines of the NSF's classification system (e.g. *Oceanology and Limnology*) were formed by the related and overlapping journals. This discipline is aligned to various FOS disciplines.
- FOS has many residual categories (e.g. *Other Social Science*), whereas Fachsystematik does not, likely due to its originally intended use case of evaluating grant proposals. Mapping from the Fachsystematik to one of these residual categories results in a loss of information.

It is important to note that in this work, we are working with the assumption that discipline classification systems developed for other means (e.g., journals) can work for datasets as well. Additionally, these case studies build on the assumption that subject metadata can traverse different levels and that a dataset can inherit this information from its container (e.g., the repository) or by proxy (e.g., from the journal of the publication it was linked to). These assumptions are something we need to validate empirically. In future work, we plan to examine how accurate the results of such mapping efforts are when applied to real world data.

As an alternative to manual mapping and classification, automated approaches to discipline classification using machine learning methods could be a fruitful path for future work to follow (Rivest et al., 2021). These approaches have been shown to have great promise in the area of assigning discipline classification, with potentially having the ability to outperform human classification (Goh et al., 2020). However, there is a great deal of work that needs to be done before this can be realistically adopted by the community (Golub, 2021). One critical question is: should a discipline classification system tell us what disciplines exist (Sjögårde & Ahlgren, 2018; Velden et al., 2017) or should these systems try to fit research outputs into existing discipline classifications (Sjögårde et al., 2021; Suominen, 2019)? While it is still unclear which methodology should be used to accomplish discipline classification through machine learning, we believe these must be open and universally adopted for them to be effective tools for studying patterns in citation and reuse of all research outputs, including datasets.

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